

The “Burst and Uplift” Tectonic Conjecture

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Abstract: This article reshapes the giant impact hypothesis from a novel perspective, providing a comprehensive description of the mechanisms behind the formation of Earth's landforms. It posits that mountains were formed from the crust's eruption and extrusion during collisions, especially secondary impacts. The oceanic crust, on the other hand, resulted from the slow hardening of magma exposed after the collision and its interaction with water, leaving clear traces. The core issue of the hypothesis also focuses on the Pacific Ring of Fire. The article conjectures that when the extraterrestrial planet "Gaia" collided with Earth, the immense impact caused the rocks of the old crust to undergo some form of high-pressure energy storage transformation, which later slowly released as thermal energy over time, forming geothermal sources that led to geothermal heat and volcanic eruptions. The formation mechanisms of trenches and volcanic island arcs are closely related to the geothermal sources in the Pacific Ring of Fire, with trenches being geothermal subsidence. Mid-ocean ridges and rift valleys are formed from the greatest forces endured by the oceanic crust as it gradually thickens, with rift valleys being the deepest fractures in the crust. The article suggests that early earthquakes were mainly due to balanced displacements, while current earthquakes are primarily caused by tidal forces and geothermal activity. The crust's ability to withstand stress is weakest at geothermal sources, thus a large number of earthquakes occur at these locations.

Keywords: high-pressure energy storage crust, geothermal source, geothermal plume, earthquake, volcano, mid-ocean ridge, trench, Scotia Sea mechanism.

0. Introduction

Although plate tectonics currently dominates the field of geotectonics, I have always found it difficult to believe in the occurrence of continental drift and seafloor spreading.

Over a decade ago, I encountered Google Earth. The ability to view the entirety of the Earth, including its seabed topography, from such close proximity was truly astonishing. At a certain moment, I suddenly felt that Google Earth could provide a glimpse into the traces of tectonic activity. After nearly ten years of observation and contemplation, I have come to believe that the hypothesis of planetary collisions offers a more plausible explanation for geological phenomena, leading to the gradual formation of the "Bursting and Uplift Tectonic Conjecture."

According to the hypothesis that the Moon was formed 4.5 billion years ago by a collision between Earth and the foreign planet "Theia," I also believe that Earth's topography was shaped by a significant collision. However, while scientists believe that Theia's collision occurred 4.5 billion years ago when the Earth's crust was still in a molten state, leaving no trace, I contend that the collision that formed the current topography occurred much later. After reviewing relevant information, I considered that one of Earth's five mass extinctions might have been caused by such a planetary collision. Additionally, I wondered whether the Cambrian explosion 500 million years ago could have been related to a major collision. Modern scientific research indicates that the age of the oceanic crust is only around 200 million years. Therefore, I hypothesize that the mass extinction at the end of the Triassic period, 200 million years ago, was caused by a collision with another celestial body, which I refer to as "Gaia." This collision, I believe, is what shaped the current Earth's topography.

The use of the mythological figure "Gaia" is an homage to "Theia" and also serves to distinguish it. A planetary collision is an extremely rare event, and I believe Earth would not have been so unfortunate as to experience two catastrophic collisions. Thus, the collision with "Theia" should be ruled out. To conclude that the Moon's existence is solely the result of a planetary collision seems unconvincing. However, the collision with "Gaia" is a more likely event, as the conjectures described in this paper seem to suggest that such a collision may have occurred.

The timing of the collision can only be speculated upon, and the description of the collision itself must remain simplistic, as it is difficult to imagine the specifics of such an event. Moreover, the catastrophic scenario is no longer of primary importance. What matters is whether the Earth we see today is the result of such a collision, and this is the core issue that this paper seeks to address.

1. Overview of the Conjecture

The discussion in this paper is based on the following hypothesis: Earth's topography was reformed after a collision with an external celestial body, referred to as "Gaia." This

collision is estimated to have occurred around 200 million years ago, with the point of impact likely being the center of the Pacific Ocean.

As shown in Figure 1, the coastline of the Pacific Ocean forms an almost perfect ring, which aligns with the basic logic of an impact formation. The collision caused Earth to fracture violently, breaking the previously intact spherical crust. The intense pressure from the impact led to the eruption and thrusting of the old crust, with some portions being uplifted or falling back down, creating towering mountain ranges, which I refer to as "uplifts."

Figure 1: Aerial view of Earth from above the Pacific Ocean, showing the ring-like shape of the Pacific coastline.

The mantle's high-temperature rock layers, exposed by the reduction in pressure, quickly melted. The collision also exposed large amounts of magma from the Earth's core. Part of the immense energy from the impact was converted into heat, melting the rock layers. The low-lying areas of Earth, formed by the subsequent coalescence of the fractured planet, turned into oceans of magma. This was followed by interactions between water and magma, sustained high temperatures, the gradual cooling of magma, and the re-differentiation and layering of the Earth's interior. These intense activities left a series of traces, which are more completely preserved in the oceanic crust. I refer to this oceanic crust as "burst," which gives rise to the term "Bursting and Uplift" used in this paper.

Since most of the continental crust is part of the original crust, with some continental shelves submerged under the sea, and certain low-lying basins potentially resulting from bursts—such as the Tarim Basin and the Sichuan Basin in China—I refer to the original crust as "old crust" and the crust formed from magma after the burst as "new crust." In short, "bursting" refers to the formation of new crust, while "uplift" refers to the mountains created by the collision.

As for the fate of the external celestial body "Gaia," part of Gaia's shell may be related to the Pacific Ring of Fire, while most of it may have merged and differentiated with Earth's internal materials. Modern geoscientists have discovered that Earth's core appears to be wrapped in an ancient, mysterious structure—namely, the Large Low-Shear-Velocity Provinces (LLSVPs) and Ultra-Low Velocity Zones (ULVZs). I believe these may represent

remnants of Gaia, as the internal differentiation and layering of the Earth have not yet fully concluded following the collision. Additionally, the droplets of geothermal source magma may also largely be remnants of Gaia.

1.1 Formation of Tectonic Plates

Earth's plate structure is unique within the solar system, but why does it have such a plate structure? The hypothesis of a massive collision makes this question self-evident. The collision, along with the resulting plate tectonics, may have been critical in creating Earth's beauty, contributing to both biodiversity and mineral diversity.

Figure 2: Crustal Structure Diagram from OneGeology.org (Ctrl + Click to view the [original](#) image and [legend](#))

The impact caused the Earth to "bloom," fracturing, shifting, and uplifting the spherical old crust, which eventually led to the formation of numerous fractured plates in the continental crust. The post-collision continental crust was highly unbalanced, initiating a process of isostatic adjustment, which in turn produced earthquakes. It is easy to imagine how frequent and catastrophic these earthquakes must have been in the early stages.

Over time, smaller plates were compressed and fused, losing their fractured nature. The fracture zones identified by scientists in the old crust today primarily correspond to still-active seismic zones. The new oceanic crust's mid-ocean ridge rift valleys are significant structural fractures, while many early fractures in the oceanic crust have already healed over time and no longer exhibit the characteristics of fracture zones. The formation mechanisms and structures of trenches and mid-ocean ridges differ greatly; some trenches may not involve fractures at all. The topography of the oceanic crust will be detailed in later chapters.

As time passed, the once-fractured and turbulent crust gradually stabilized. The combined effects of isostatic adjustment and erosion by wind and rain have caused dramatic changes in the land's topography. The Earth's interior also underwent secondary differentiation and layering. By the time humanity began to study the world, only a few active fracture zones remained, with land-based fault lines likely concentrated in regions of intense geothermal activity.

Therefore, I believe that Earth's current topography was primarily shaped by the massive collision with "Gaia," followed by isostatic deformation and centuries of erosion, rather than by continental drift and seafloor spreading.

From the crustal structure diagram in Figure 2, it is evident that the dense lines in the oceanic crust indicate that it has not been eroded by wind and rain, preserving fracture marks relatively intact. In contrast, the fracture zones of the continental crust, when viewed through the lens of the collision hypothesis, seem to appropriately reflect the forces of impact and bursting, which will be explained in detail in the next section.

Today, Earth's lithosphere has formed into several nearly equal-sized active plates, which share tidal stress almost evenly, resulting in a stable structure.

1.2 Formation of Landforms

The Earth's mountains, referred to as "uplifts," were formed instantly by the impact.

Figure 3 presents a 3D artistic representation of Earth's elevation, with some exaggeration to provide a clearer view of the topography. Additionally, the way the map is unfolded results in a significant discrepancy between the illustrated positions and the actual locations.

Figure 3: 3D Elevation Map of Earth. Base map sourced from the internet [\[Original Image\]](#) [\[Topographic Map\]](#)

1.2.1 Mountains Formed by Direct Impact:

The Rocky Mountains in North America and the Andes in South America were formed directly by the collision with "Gaia."

The mountain ranges along the Pacific coast of Antarctica, the islands of New Guinea in the western Pacific, the Philippines, Taiwan, the Japanese archipelago, the Kamchatka

Peninsula, and the Aleutian Islands—all within the Pacific Ring of Fire—are the result of "Gaia" impacting Earth's crust. This ring-shaped region represents the contact line where "Gaia" struck, and it reflects the remnants of "Gaia" and the old crust interacting with the magma ocean and water vapor, along with subsequent geothermal and volcanic activity. The unique landforms of this area will be explained in detail in the sections on the Pacific Ring of Fire and oceanic topography.

From **Figure 3**, it is evident that "Gaia" struck Earth at an angle, slanting toward the Americas. The opening of the Atlantic Ocean occurred near the impact point, with the eastern edge of the Pacific Ocean in the Americas uplifting due to the impact, while the western edge of the Pacific Ocean subsided. All of these observations align with the logic of an oblique impact.

1.2.2 Mountains Formed by Secondary Impacts

Figure 4: Mountains formed by secondary impacts. [Original Image]

a. The Himalayas and the Tibetan Plateau were formed by the secondary impact of the Indian Plate, which fell from high altitude after the initial collision, causing uplift.

b. The Zagros Mountains and the Iranian Plateau resulted from secondary impacts of the Arabian Plate.

c. When the Arabian Plate fell, it also fractured the African continent, creating the East African Rift Valley and the island of Madagascar.

d. The Alps and the Dinaric Alps were formed by the secondary impact of the Italian Plate.

e. The Iberian Peninsula might also be a landmass that descended from above. See Figures 3 and 4.

f. Greenland might have moved from the Arctic Ocean to its current position. The arc-shaped coastline of Norway and the arc along Baffin Bay are also consistent with this. See Figure 5.

g. These secondary impacts may have caused secondary fracturing of the crust. For example, local areas such as the Mediterranean, the Black Sea, the Caspian Sea, the Tarim Basin, and the Sichuan Basin might have experienced secondary fracturing, which contributed to the formation of surrounding mountain ranges.

The large light-colored desert region stretching from North Africa to East Asia, apart from its arid climate, likely consists of areas that slowly rose above sea level after the collision. This scenario suggests that secondary collisions among several continental plates during the impact led to depressions in the crust, which were later modified by secondary differentiation and isostatic adjustment within the Earth, resulting in the current topography. This process caused significant changes in land and seafloor elevation and is a fundamental reason for the dramatic transformation of landscapes. See Figure 4.

Figure 5: Greenland. [\[Original Image\]](#)

1.2.3 Mountains Formed Indirectly:

The remaining mountain ranges and uplifts were primarily formed by the pushing and uplifting of the old crust during the collision and secondary impacts with "Gaia."

The Eurasian continent experienced significant uplift between the western Pacific coast and the southern shores of the Arctic Ocean, resulting in a series of characteristic uplifts. For instance, the Changbai Mountains and the Wuyi Mountains arc are uplifts on the Pacific side, while the Daxinganling, Taihang, Qinling, and Qilian mountain ranges were formed by the compressive forces of the collision.

The Tianshan and Altai Mountains in northern China, along with the Outer Baikal Mountains in Russia, are uplifts formed by the pressures from the Arctic Ocean side. The Ural Mountains were formed by the east-west compressive forces.

The Qilian Mountains might have been pushed away from their original arc due to secondary impacts from the Indian Plate.

1.2.4 Sichuan Basin:

Given that the Sichuan Basin may have resulted from secondary fracturing, the crust here should be similar to the oceanic crust. Are there similar fold structures in the oceanic crust? Yes, there are many! This indicates that the folded mountains in the Sichuan Basin and the Chongqing region were formed by the expansion and compression of the crust as magma cooled after the basin's fracturing. This will be further explained in the section on oceanic topography. See **Figure 6**.

Figure 6: Folds and uplifts in the Sichuan Basin.

For a better understanding of global mountain terrain formation, readers are encouraged to apply the "Bursting and Uplifting Conjecture" principles, and refer to **Figure 2** for crustal structure, to observe and contemplate these features, which may lead to valuable insights.

1.3 Core Issue of Tectonics: The Pacific Ring of Fire, Geothermal Sources, Volcanoes, and Earthquakes

The Pacific Ring of Fire is renowned for its numerous volcanic chains and island arcs in the ocean, as well as for being the site of the majority of the world's earthquakes. The question of why the Pacific Ring of Fire exists and what it fundamentally represents has become a core issue in tectonics, with all theories and models striving to provide a reasonable explanation for this phenomenon.

The plate tectonics theory explains it as follows: "The subducting crust penetrates into the asthenosphere, where the subducted plate melts, supplying magma for volcanic activity at the trench edges. This magma rises and erupts at the surface, forming arc-shaped volcanic chains."

Since I do not subscribe to the plate tectonics theory, I cannot accept this explanation of the Ring of Fire's formation. Thus, I need to present my own ideas to complete this discussion. Since I started writing this paper in 2016, I have continuously thought about this issue, which indeed poses a major challenge and complex problem. My hypotheses may be rudimentary, but the consistent thought is that geothermal sources originate from crustal radiogenic heat rather than from the mantle, and that geothermal sources drive various crustal activities, including volcanic and seismic events. I will propose a conjecture based on the collision hypothesis, aiming for logical coherence, with the validation of this conjecture relying on future scientific research.

Recently, I have reviewed several useful scientific materials, such as the seismological fluorescence map by John Nelson (Figure 7), the global volcanic distribution map (Figure 8), and the global hot springs map (Figure 9). It can be observed that the distribution densities of global volcanoes, hot springs, and earthquakes in recent decades tend to overlap. The seismological fluorescence map in Figure 7 resembles an X-ray image, vividly illustrating the geothermal sources within the crust. I will explain the relationship between earthquakes and geothermal sources. It should be noted that this data only reflects the seismic situation of the past 100 years, and earlier conditions, particularly in the early years following the major collision, were likely quite different.

Figure 7: Seismological Fluorescence Map Since 1898. Created by John Nelson. [\[Original Image\]](#)

Figure 8: Global Volcanic Distribution Map and Major Earthquake Locations. From the internet. [\[Original Image\]](#)

Figure 9: Global Hot Springs Distribution Map. Image sourced from the internet. [\[Original Image\]](#)

1.3.1 On Geothermal Sources

As mentioned earlier, the geothermal sources in the continental crust originate from radiogenic heat activities within the crust, rather than from mantle heat activities. For example, the revival of extinct volcanoes cannot be attributed to long-term mantle heat targeting a specific volcanic vent; only with a radiogenic mechanism within the crust can we adequately explain such phenomena. This radiogenic activity in the crust is fundamental to the Pacific Ring of Fire and to geothermal sources in other regions.

The Pacific Ring of Fire is the contact line of the planetary collision. When "Gaia" collided with Earth, the immense impact altered the rocks in the crust. Within certain distances from the impact contact line, the rocks underwent a high-pressure phase transformation—either an increase in radioactive materials or some unknown energy increase. Over the subsequent long period, this energy was gradually released as heat, forming geothermal sources. This radiogenic heat reaction led to localized melting of rocks, creating magma chambers. As thermal energy increased, these chambers gradually expanded and interconnected, forming magma lakes. Due to the differentiation of magma,

heavier magma progressively penetrated and dropped to deeper layers, with some even reaching the core. This process formed geothermal columns and the Low-Seismic-Velocity Provinces (LLSVP) and Ultra-Low-Velocity Zones (ULVZ) at the core-mantle boundary. Lighter magma, due to its varying density, settled at different depths, with light magma being the source of volcanic eruptions.

Geothermal columns and the so-called mantle plumes are the same phenomenon but in opposite growth directions (though I am still unclear whether the concept of mantle plumes is a hypothesis or supported by concrete scientific evidence). Due to the fusion of Earth with "Gaia" and the subsequent long-term differentiation and layering processes, LLSVPs and ULVZs might be incomplete layering products. These zones, having higher temperatures compared to their surroundings, have densities that keep them confined, but they may eventually merge with the mantle and core, potentially disappearing over time. Thus, geothermal columns would be widely distributed along geothermal sources, with varying depths and lifecycles, which explains the diversity of volcanic magma.

The seismological fluorescence map shows that the Pacific Ring of Fire is the brightest area, indicating the impact-affected regions of the old crust with stored energy. The areas influenced by the secondary impacts of the Indian Plate, the Arabian Plate, the Italian Plate, and the Iberian Plate formed the Himalaya-Mediterranean volcanic chain. Due to the significant differences in impact forces, the energy levels of stored energy and radiogenic heat in the crust also vary greatly. As the distance from the impact contact line increases, the stored energy and radiogenic heat decrease rapidly, as illustrated in **Figure 7**.

The intensity and timing of geothermal heat should be closely related. The earliest and most intense radiogenic heat likely originated from the impact surface of "Gaia," forming the oceanic trenches and troughs of the Pacific Ring of Fire, as well as the continental crust subsidence along the coasts, such as the California Basin. The geothermal subsidence in oceanic topography will be further described.

There are two types of geothermal sources in the oceanic crust: One is the geothermal sources of the Pacific Ring of Fire, originating from high-pressure, stored old crust. The other is the geothermal sources from mid-ocean ridge rift valleys, similar to the East African Rift Valley. These rift zones represent true crustal lithospheric fractures, leading to the asthenosphere, with geothermal sources originating from deep within the crust and reaching the asthenosphere, with heat exchanges involving seawater. This will be described in the formation of mid-ocean ridges.

Figure 10: Seismic Wave Velocities and Earth's Internal Layer Structure. Created by Dahu. [\[Original Image\]](#)

Sidebar (Contrary to Mainstream Views):

As shown in **Figure 10**, the Earth's internal structure from the crust to the Gutenberg Discontinuity is about 2,900 km thick and is predominantly solid. Only the 65-225 km depth is the asthenosphere, which has plasticity, suggesting that the crust and mantle function as a unified whole. The outer core, from 2,900 to 5,120 km deep, is 2,120 km thick and is in a liquid state. The inner core, from 5,120 to 6,370 km deep, is a solid high-density metallic sphere with a radius of 1,250 km and a diameter of 2,500 km. This structure has formed through billions of years of differentiation and layering and is a stable configuration. As depth increases, both the density and temperature of the material increase, making it difficult for the system to become chaotic without external forces.

I came across a schematic diagram online depicting the idea of mantle material sinking due to cooling and rising due to heating. I find this concept difficult to understand. The position of Earth's internal materials is determined by density rather than temperature; deeper regions are hotter, so mantle convection is hard to justify (in the atmosphere, airflow is also driven by density rather than temperature, though this is debatable). Seafloor spreading is even more difficult to justify. Mid-ocean ridge rifts are fractures leading to the asthenosphere, but these fractures are tightly compressed and can only shift slightly to relieve stress, so there is no justification for seafloor spreading.

Similarly, the notion of continental drift is questionable. The major plates of the Earth's crust fit together almost perfectly, forming a solid rock layer 5-30 km thick. It is hard to imagine how they could move relative to each other.

If mantle plumes are definitively proven to exist through scientific methods, I would consider them as geothermal columns moving from top to bottom rather than from bottom to top.

The Earth's internal heat balance is easily self-regulated, primarily through changes in the volume of the liquid outer core. Given its enormous volume, even minor changes can adequately balance significant thermal variations.

1.3.2 About Volcanoes

Currently, the origins of geothermal activity, hot springs, and volcanoes are all related to geothermal sources. When gases or water vapor are trapped within a magma chamber, the likelihood of a volcanic eruption increases. Trapped gases raise the pressure, and the thermal conductivity of the gases can cause the crust to melt upwards. A volcanic eruption occurs to release the pressure generated by the geothermal source. Once the pressure is released, the volcano ceases activity. If there isn't a significant amount of gas generated or trapped, the pressure in the magma chamber may not be sufficient to break through the crust, resulting in geothermal activity without a volcanic eruption.

The presence of a geothermal plume is related to the composition and temperature of the magma, but it does not directly determine whether a volcanic eruption will occur. Volcanoes with geothermal plumes can have prolonged eruptions because the direct connection to the mantle and the decompression of the geothermal plume increase the amount of magma melting in the mantle. This results in longer eruptions and a larger

volume of erupted material. The depth of the geothermal plume also affects the composition of volcanic materials, leading to different types of volcanoes.

This understanding helps explain why volcanoes go through periods of dormancy and reactivation, as well as their various characteristics. The formation of volcanic chains is linked to the distribution of geothermal sources. In regions such as the Pacific Ring of Fire, where geothermal sources are connected, the formation of one volcano and its eruption releases pressure locally, preventing new volcanoes from forming at certain distances. Hence, volcanic chains are often spaced at intervals.

The formation of volcanoes along mid-ocean ridges may differ from other volcanic mechanisms. Here, fissures extend directly into the mantle's asthenosphere, and volcanic magma may ascend from the asthenosphere due to decompression. This phenomenon may be due to cooling issues, which I refer to as a "mid-ocean ridge fissure healing Sequelae." Volcanoes in Iceland, Hawaii, and the East African Rift might follow a similar mechanism.

Contrary to the plate tectonics theory, mid-ocean ridges are not discrete boundaries but regions under immense compressive pressure. Although these fissures reach the asthenosphere, true volcanic eruptions are relatively rare. Thus, the current state of volcanic activity differs significantly from the early stages following the great collision, a topic that will be explored further in the section on oceanic landscapes.

1.3.3 About Earthquakes

The causes of earthquakes can be quite complex, but in simplified terms, early earthquakes were primarily caused by isostatic adjustments. Nowadays, tidal forces from the Moon and the Sun are likely the main drivers of earthquakes, with geothermal activity also being a contributing factor.

In the early stages after Earth's collision and re-aggregation, the planet had a rugged landscape with significant variations in crustal thickness. Under the influence of crustal gravity and internal re-differentiation processes, earthquakes of varying sizes gradually led to a more balanced and stable state. Elevated regions subsided, and depressed areas rose, resulting in dramatic geological changes over time.

As time passed, isostatic adjustments may have been largely completed. However, tidal forces from the Moon and the Sun continue to cause fluctuations in stress on the Earth's crust. When these stresses reach a critical threshold and exceed the crust's strength, earthquakes occur due to relative displacement.

The forces that cause earthquakes are primarily vertical, released along fault lines. The crust may experience significant horizontal compressive stress, which can actually inhibit seismic activity. The early horizontal compressive forces responsible for folding the crust demonstrate their impact.

Earthquakes occur along fault lines because these zones are weaker points where large, differently stressed crustal regions are subjected to vertical shear or tension forces. Fault lines are more likely to experience relative displacement and release substantial amounts of energy.

The frequent occurrence of earthquakes during volcanic eruptions indicates that geothermal activity can also trigger earthquakes, especially deep-seated ones, which might be solely caused by geothermal processes.

Currently, most earthquakes occur in geothermal source regions. Fault lines in these areas are particularly weak due to the reduced rigidity of the crust. Even in regions with widespread and shallow geothermal activity, there is a possibility of localized faulting, even if not associated with collision fault lines.

Geothermal source regions like the Pacific Ring of Fire, with potential melt connectivity within the crust, experience more frequent geothermal activity, making their crustal rigidity the weakest. Thus, the Pacific Ring of Fire is both a geothermal and seismic zone. As seen in Figure 8, the weakened Pacific Ring of Fire has led to a stronger Pacific crust, with many early fissures healed and no longer forming expected mid-ocean ridges.

Major earthquakes, such as those with a magnitude of 7 or above, predominantly occur in the Pacific Ring of Fire and the Himalayas-Mediterranean seismic chain. Mid-ocean ridge fissures, being more vulnerable and easier to relieve stress, experience frequent but lower-magnitude earthquakes.

Logically, the positions of the Moon and the Sun, along with atmospheric pressure changes, are factors that trigger earthquakes. They can alter the stress accumulated in fault lines, serving as the proverbial last straw.

Thus, the earthquake fluorescence map over the past century can be metaphorically compared to an X-ray of the Earth's geothermal sources, providing a reasonable analogy.

1.4 Formation of Oceanic Topography

In this section, I will explain the formation mechanism of oceanic topography based on the Big Collision Hypothesis and the geothermal source concepts discussed earlier.

1.4.1 Formation Mechanism of Ocean Trenches

Ocean trenches are primarily formed within the Pacific Ring of Fire and can be understood as geothermal subsidence features. The trenches, along with the land-based basins such as the California Basin, represent varying degrees of geothermal subsidence at different times.

Following the high-pressure, energy-storage transformation of the crust caused by the Big Collision, during a period of secondary differentiation and cooling of the Earth's layers, the high-pressure, energy-storage crust of the Pacific Ring of Fire, or the remnants of "Gaia," releases a significant amount of heat. This leads to the gradual formation of interconnected magma lakes that melt and sink deeper into the Earth's layers, causing the crust to subside and form oceanic trenches.

It is possible that the rocks scraped and left behind during the collision of "Gaia" had higher energy storage and density. As they melted and subsided into the mantle or even the core, they contributed to the formation of the Low-Velocity Super-Prismatic (LLSVP) and Ultra-Low-Velocity Zone (ULVZ) regions at the core-mantle boundary. These regions may be composed of magma from "Gaia" that has not yet completed its differentiation, remaining at the core-mantle boundary due to its density.

Figure 11: Western Pacific Topography - Erratic Movements of the Fire Circle Crust Driven by Steam in the Magma Ocean

The geothermal sources of the volcanic chains and island arcs associated with ocean trenches are produced by the slower release of energy from the older crust in the Pacific Ring of Fire. This is particularly due to the melting of the old crust, which results in magma remaining in the shallow crust due to density factors.

Logically speaking, if oceanic crust was being inserted into the mantle through seafloor spreading, such vertical oceanic trenches would not form. Instead, the morphology would resemble the posture of the Indian Plate and the Himalayas. Figure 11 shows the complex trench formations in the western Pacific, which are difficult to explain with plate tectonic theory. Additionally, if the formation of the Pacific Ring of Fire were solely due to oceanic crust insertion, where would the discrete boundaries in the center of the Pacific be? And why do we not see similar oceanic crust insertion into continental crust in the orderly divergent ridges of the Atlantic Ocean?

1.4.2 Formation Mechanism of Volcanic Island Arcs—Formation of the Scotia Sea Oceanic Crust

The Scotia Sea oceanic crust, situated between South America and Antarctica, features a unique topography that resembles a river bursting its banks, which is clearly not caused by ocean currents and is challenging to explain using plate tectonic theory. Although I have abandoned the previous hypothesis that magma and steam interactions form ocean trenches, and thus have given up explaining the Scotia Sea oceanic crust formation through that mechanism, the excitement and joy of my earlier thoughts on steam-driven formation of the Scotia Sea oceanic crust remain unforgettable. This is one of the

main reasons I am reluctant to abandon improving this paper. Therefore, I continue to uphold the hypothesis that steam drove the formation of the Scotia Sea topography.

After the Big Collision, the initial old crust of South America and Antarctica was connected, but it was very thin. When water interacted with high-temperature magma to produce steam, the residual high-pressure energy storage crust from "Gaia" at the collision zone, likely around the ocean trench formation area, would have a higher temperature than the surrounding magma. This resulted in a higher vapor pressure and greater reaction force. The substantial difference in steam reaction force between the Pacific and Atlantic sides would have ruptured this weak old crust and then gradually pushed it towards the Atlantic side until it reached its current position. The residual "Gaia" and some of the old crust were gradually buried within the oceanic crust. The fore-arc trench, like other trenches, was also formed by the geothermal subsidence of the residual "Gaia" crust; similarly, the volcanic island arc is a result of the gradual heat release of the old crust with different energy storage embedded in the oceanic crust.

In reality, the water depth at that time is unknown, but currently, the water depth ranges from over 2,000 meters to over 4,000 meters. The nature of steam in deep water is unclear, and it might resemble cavitation phenomena, where bubbles form and then collapse, releasing energy and generating thrust.

The formation of the Scotia Sea oceanic crust can only be roughly described in this manner because the specific conditions after the collision are difficult to deduce, and my own knowledge and imagination fall short in providing a reasonable and convincing description to the readers. Regardless of the exact conditions, the result is that steam drove the movement of the Pacific Ring of Fire's energy-storage crust in this area.

Thus, although the South Sandwich Islands arc and trench are located in the Atlantic Ocean, they are actually products of the Pacific Ring of Fire. The above description is referred to as the formation mechanism of the Scotia Sea oceanic crust and is applicable to all volcanic island arcs. See Figure 12.

1.4.3 Formation of Other Volcanic Island Arcs Based on the Scotia Sea Oceanic Crust Formation Mechanism

To illustrate the plausibility of the Scotia Sea oceanic crust formation mechanism, I have taken screenshots of relevant parts of my so-called geothermal X-ray image for comparison. Refer to Figure 7.

Figure 12: Scotia Sea Oceanic Crust and the South Sandwich Islands Volcanic Island Arc. The steam has moved the Ring of Fire crust approximately 2,500 kilometers.

(1) Scotia Sea Oceanic Crust and South Sandwich Islands Volcanic Island Arc

The Scotia Sea oceanic crust and the South Sandwich Islands volcanic island arc have been displaced approximately 2,500 kilometers by steam. See Figure 12.

(2) Caribbean Sea and the Lesser Antilles Volcanic Island Arc

The Caribbean Sea and the Lesser Antilles volcanic island arc have also been displaced approximately 2,500 kilometers by steam, despite being located in the Atlantic Ocean. This indicates that they are still products of the Pacific Ring of Fire. See Figure 13.

Figure 13: Volcanic island arc in the Caribbean and terminal Lesser Antilles. Move 2500 km.

(3) Philippine Sea and Mariana Volcanic Island Arc

The Philippine Sea and the Mariana volcanic island arc have been displaced approximately 2,500 kilometers by steam as well. See Figure 14.

Figure 14: Philippine Sea, Mariana volcanic island arc. Steam propelled the crust of the ring of fire to move 2,500 kilometers.

The fact that these regions have been displaced by approximately the same distance of 2,500 kilometers lends support to the correctness of the Scotia Sea formation mechanism, as they occurred and ceased almost simultaneously. Although 2,500 kilometers seems like a vast distance, it is not unreasonable considering the destructive nature of planetary collisions and the grand scale of magma exposure.

Clearly, the West Pacific Ring of Fire differs significantly from the American coastline. As previously mentioned, the variation is due to the oblique impact of "Gaia," which led to the fracturing and subsidence of the west coast crust, resulting in more chaotic interactions with steam.

(4) Australia's Unexpected Location

Figure 15 displays the distorted Solomon Islands Ring of Fire, the grand rotation of the Fiji-Tonga Ring of Fire, and the incredible Sunda Arc Ring of Fire. Clearly, these regions' Ring of Fire crusts were likely split from a possible collision line and were moved to their current locations by steam. This can also be understood from the structure of the Ring of Fire in the Philippine Sea. Later observations of the deep Diamantina Trench in the Indian Ocean and remnants on the seafloor suggest that the Sunda Arc might have been pushed from the original Ring of Fire crust. This possibility better explains the existence of such deep oceanic trenches in the Indian Ocean, as they are also related to the geothermal subsidence of the Pacific Ring of Fire crust.

Figure 15: Australia's Unexpected Location. [Original Image](#)

Australia's placement appears unexpected, but it fits within the context of these explanations.

The presence of the Australian continent complicates the hypothesis. The existence of Australia seems to defy the expectation of a complete Pacific Ring of Fire system. In this case, if Australia is considered a continent that emerged slowly from the ocean of magma, it might resolve the inconsistency. Australia could be a piece of old crust that was driven into the Earth's interior by the impact of "Gaia," and, due to its relatively lower density and incomplete melting, it gradually floated up from the oceanic crust. By the time the Australian continent emerged, the Ring of Fire topography had already been established, turning what seemed impossible into a possible scenario. Although this hypothesis seems far-fetched, it could potentially explain the anomaly.

For other Ring of Fire topographies, the Scotia Sea oceanic crust formation mechanism can be used as a reference to investigate the features of regions showing traces of magma disturbances.

Thus, the Pacific Ring of Fire can be understood as a nearly complete and closed ring, making the hypothesis of the great collision a more coherent explanation.

(5) Madagascar Island

Similarly, when the Arabian Peninsula block fell and caused the East African Rift, it also split off Madagascar Island. In this case, steam pushed Madagascar Island away from the East African continent. See Figure 16.

Figure 16: East African Rift and Madagascar Island

The above description provides insight into how other volcanic island arcs may have formed based on the Scotia Sea oceanic crust formation mechanism.

1.4.4 Formation Mechanisms of Mid-Ocean Ridges, Oceanic Crust Folds, and Seamounts

After the collision, magma interacting with water eventually cooled and solidified to form new crust. Throughout the process of solidification, which transitioned from thin to thick crust, various forces acted, leading to the formation of different geological features in stages.

I hypothesize that during the cooling and solidification of oceanic crust, the first features to form were seafloor folds and seamounts, followed by the gradual formation of mid-ocean ridges and rift valleys. Clearly, the steam-driven movement of the Pacific Ring of Fire crust occurred before the solidification of the oceanic crust.

(1) Formation Mechanism of Oceanic Crust Folds

It can be said that the surface of the oceanic crust, excluding sedimentary layers, is not flat. I believe this is due to two main factors: first, the result of magma and steam interaction; and second, the folds formed during the solidification process of the oceanic crust due to expansion and compression.

The seafloor topography on Google Earth may differ significantly from reality, with only a few straight lines resembling tread marks being more accurately mapped by ship surveys (I only discovered this truth in April 2024). For example, Figure 17a shows a local area of the mid-ocean ridge with a height difference of about 500 meters between folds; Figure 17b shows a local area outside the mid-ocean ridge with a height difference of about 150 meters between folds. The height difference data are obtained by reading the altitude difference with a mouse hover, and its accuracy is uncertain, but it illustrates the issue. One striking point is the ruggedness of the seafloor, indicating that navigating such terrain would be extremely challenging for humans.

There is no exact research result available online about whether the oceanic crust contracts, expands, or remains unchanged in volume during solidification. Perhaps I simply haven't found it yet. From existing images of oceanic crust, I believe that the volume of basaltic oceanic crust should expand during the solidification and crystallization process; only expansion would lead to the formation of such folds.

Plate tectonic theory might explain these folds as a result of magma rising from mid-ocean ridge rift valleys, causing seafloor expansion. I think that in the early stages of oceanic crust solidification, a large amount of magma rose through various fissures, but the magma didn't have the force to expand the oceanic crust. Later on, magma rising through the fissures decreased significantly.

Figure 17: Seafloor Folds a: Mid-Ocean Ridge Folds b: Folds Outside the Mid-Ocean Ridge

(2) Formation Mechanism of Seamounts

Global Seamount Distribution Map based on Altimetric Data. When examining the seamount survey map in Figure 18, I was astonished to discover the vast number of seamounts on the seafloor. The statistics reveal 24,643 seamounts ranging from 100 meters to approximately 4,000 meters in height. Some of these seamounts clearly exhibit volcanic features, while others seem to be mere rounded mounds without volcanic characteristics. My view is that these seamounts were also formed in stages during the oceanic crust formation process: the lower seamounts formed earlier, and the taller ones formed later. Importantly, seamounts lower than 100 meters may not be displayed due to resolution issues and sediment coverage, suggesting that even smaller seamounts are likely scattered across the seafloor.

During the initial stages of a planetary collision, the new crust formed at the explosion site began to cool and thicken from scratch. As a thin oceanic crust developed, it trapped the dispersal of magma, water vapor, and other gases. Frequent bulging occurred on this thin crust. The initial bulges were very dense, and after breaking, they would flatten again. However, as time passed, the crust thickened and cooled, leading to a decrease in the frequency of bulges but an increase in their size. When the gas in these bulges escaped, they could not revert to their original state, resulting in the seamounts we see today. Eventually, bulge energy levels increased and the spacing between bulges widened. Most of these bulges were essentially small volcanoes venting gas and magma from the original

smaller mounds. When the crust thickened to a certain extent, this mountain-building activity largely ceased, but volcanic activity from crustal expansion and stretching continued.

Figure 18: Seamount Map [Original Image](#)

Image Description: This study determined the global distribution of 24,643 potential seamounts. Black dots ($n = 16,185$) represent seamounts with heights $0.1 \leq h < 1$ km; blue dots ($n = 7,514$) represent seamounts with heights $1 \leq h < 3$ km; red dots ($n = 944$) represent seamounts with heights $h \geq 3$ km. Plate boundaries (Bird 2003) are shown as gray lines, and seamount exclusion zones (SEZs) are delineated by black lines. The inset shows the histogram of seamount height distribution.

Figure 19: Seafloor Plateau Map [Original Image](#)

As shown in Figure 19, many of the seafloor plateaus are likely remnants of early volcanic activity caused by magma upwelling. Some may also be remnants of older crust that fell into the explosion site during the collision. I encountered research articles discussing the presence of granite in oceanic crust, which researchers struggle to explain. This contradicts seafloor spreading theory but supports the planetary collision hypothesis.

Regarding many flat-topped volcano remnants on the seafloor, the Busting and Uplift tectonic hypothesis suggests that after a planetary collision, the surface elevation would have been significantly different from today. If the Himalayas had also been impacted into the seabed, the depth of the Pacific Ocean would have differed greatly from now. Volcanoes exposed at that time could have been flattened by ocean waves, creating flat-topped seamounts as the earth's surface shifted over time. As the earth adjusted, mountain ranges rose and the seafloor sank, transforming these volcanoes into flat-topped seamounts.

The Busting and Uplift tectonic hypothesis consistently provides reasonable explanations for known phenomena on Earth.

(3) Formation Mechanism of Mid-Ocean Ridges and Rifts

During the process of oceanic crust solidification and thickening, various forces cause the crust to experience bulging, compression, and rifting. In the later stages of new crust formation and as the Earth's internal layered structure gradually stabilizes, only the areas under the greatest stress will continue to rift, while other areas cease to split. Therefore, the areas with the most stress are typically the central line regions (a structural mechanics concept), leading to the formation of the mid-ocean ridges and rifts we observe today.

Figure 20: Mid-Atlantic Ridge and Rift Diagram [Original Image](#)

The transverse cracks on the mid-ocean ridge seen today are the result of continued compression, longitudinal reciprocating displacement, and friction along the ridge rift during the cooling and thickening of the oceanic crust. The persistent displacement and transverse cracking in the ridge rift allow seawater to seep into these fissures, causing the crust in these areas to cool and extend deeper into the mantle compared to other areas. Due to seawater cooling, the oceanic crust here has difficulty melting and recovering, making it thicker than elsewhere. This thickening eventually leads to uplift, forming the ridge as seen in **Figure 20**.

From **Figure 7**, it is evident that currently, only the rift is an active fault zone along the mid-ocean ridge, while other cracks show no signs of activity, indicating they are

archaeological remnants of the crust formation process and are no longer active. After the crust solidifies, the expansion force largely disappears, but the tidal forces continue to act regularly. The tidal tension is insufficient to keep other regions' faults active, while the ridge rift fault zone endures the greatest tension, making it difficult for the rift to heal and close. The continual seismic activity at the rift releases stress, which also explains the rarity of large earthquakes along the mid-ocean ridge.

From Figure 21, the global surface heat flow map indicates that the seawater infiltrates and exchanges heat with high-temperature rocks in the deeper crust, which should not be considered as a result of magma upwelling. The land portions of the heat flow map may not accurately reflect the true geothermal sources due to limitations in depth and scale relative to surface heat flow measurements.

Figure 21: Global Surface Heat Flow and Volcano Map [Original Image](#)

Image Description: This map shows global surface heat flow and volcanic activity.

According to Figure 22, the solidus temperature of rocks in the deep mid-ocean ridge and rift areas might be relatively low due to higher water content, making the rocks softer. The strong compressive forces on both sides of the rift might contribute to the easier uplift of the mid-ocean ridge. Thus, the mid-ocean ridge crust is thicker and softer compared to other areas.

Figure 22: Rock Solidus Line: A diagram showing the solidus temperature lines for rocks. [Original Image](#)

Examining Figure 18, the seamount map, reveals important information. The 16,185 black dots representing seamounts below 1,000 meters are likely groups of bulging seamounts formed during the crust thickening process, predominantly found on small transverse fissures of the mid-ocean ridge. The 7,514 blue dots, ranging from 1 to 3 kilometers, appear in large transverse fissures of the Pacific Ring of Fire and mid-ocean ridges, with some in the central and western Pacific. The 944 red dots, larger than 3 kilometers, represent extensions of the blue dots, with some forming continuous lines. These lines clearly indicate former rift zones that have healed over time, such as the Hawaiian Islands' chain, which was once connected to the Atlantic-Arctic rift. The distribution of these seamounts and fissures reflects their formation stages, supporting the hypothesis of initially small seamounts becoming larger over time.

From Figure 7 and Figure 21, global active fault zones like the Pacific Ring of Fire, the Mediterranean-Himalayan belt, and mid-ocean ridge rifts divide the crust surface into roughly equal major plates, distributing tidal stress evenly and achieving a stable state.

Regarding the scientifically confirmed symmetrical magnetic anomalies along the mid-ocean ridges and the proportional relationship between crustal age and distance to the mid-ocean ridge rift, can we find rationality in the formation patterns of seamounts and rifts?

2 Summary

This paper, based on the planetary collision hypothesis, outlines the formation mechanisms of Earth's geomorphology following the impact of the celestial body "Gaia." Although the specifics of whether "Gaia" and "Theia" were the same entity or the exact timing of the collision remain ambiguous, the core belief is that tectonic features originate from this major planetary collision.

Main Points of the Hypothesis:

1. **Earth's Geomorphology Post-Collision:** Earth's landforms are products of a planetary collision. Concepts such as continental drift and seafloor spreading are difficult to explain otherwise. Currently, the Earth's internal layered structure is in a relatively stable state, with no ongoing mantle convection.

2. **Mountain Formation:** Mountains formed from the explosion and uplift of the crust during the collision, particularly from secondary impacts leading to uplift—referred to as "Bursting and Uplift." The oceanic crust, on the other hand, formed from the interaction between magma and water post-collision, gradually solidifying from thin to thick—referred to as "Bursting and Uplift."

3. **Seamounts, Crustal Rifts, Mid-Ocean Ridges, and Sea Floor Folds:** These features formed in stages during the development of the oceanic crust. Due to constant tidal forces from the Moon and Sun, mid-ocean ridges and rifts have become the final channels for crustal stress release, making full healing difficult.

'Bursting and Uplifting' Tectonic Conjecture

Build by Dahu 20240806

Figure 23: The "Busting and Uplift" Tectonic Conjecture [Original Image1](#) [Original Image2](#)

4. **Geothermal Sources and Volcanoes:** The Pacific Ring of Fire is the contact line of the planetary collision. The massive impact of "Gaia" induced high-pressure transformations in ancient crustal rocks, which slowly released as thermal energy, creating geothermal sources and volcanic activity. This explains the Pacific Ring of Fire (direct collision) and the Mediterranean-Himalayan belt (secondary impacts).

5. **Oceanic Trenches:** These are the earliest large-scale geothermal depressions in the Pacific Ring of Fire. The heat source continues to melt and drop, forming geothermal columns. Low-velocity zones (LLSVP) and ultra-low-velocity zones (ULVZ) might be remnants of "Gaia" and the ongoing residuals of geothermal magma.

6. **Scotia Sea Oceanic Crust Formation Mechanism:** Similar volcanic island arcs and oceanic crust features in the Pacific and Atlantic, shaped by steam-driven high-pressure crust movement in a magma ocean, are explained by the Scotia Sea Oceanic Crust Formation Mechanism. This extends to the entire Pacific volcanic arcs and Western Pacific crustal disturbances.

7. **Earthquake Mechanisms:** Earthquakes result from the release of immense crustal stress. Early post-collision earthquakes were major adjustments, while current seismic activities mainly release tidal stress and are milder. Most earthquakes concentrate in geothermally active regions, with deep-focus earthquakes possibly linked to geothermal magma drop-offs.

8. **Volcanoes and Geothermal Sources:** Persistent geothermal sources do not always result in volcanic activity. Volcanoes erupt when geothermal chambers seal gases and steam. Oceanic volcanoes are linked to the oceanic crust formation process, and modern volcanoes (e.g., Iceland, Hawaii) might be **Sequelae** of healed crustal fissures.

9. **Earth's Lithospheric Plates:** The lithosphere has formed approximately equal-sized tectonic plates, evenly distributing tidal or other stresses, achieving a relatively stable structure.

Refer to **Figures 3 and 23** for diagrams of the "Bursting and Uplift" tectonic conjecture.

3 Afterword

This paper can be viewed as a comprehensive science fiction narrative on tectonics, rather than a conventional scientific paper. The article primarily relies on images from Google Earth and other online sources, and while Google Earth offers a grand and detailed view, it can also present discrepancies with real-world conditions, particularly in oceanic topography.

The idea for this paper emerged from the perception that continental drift and seafloor spreading seemed implausible. Since the initial draft in 2016, the paper has undergone years of continuous thought and revision, with many changes and refinements leading to the current viewpoints.

Though this counter-current paper may not align with mainstream and orthodox theories, it is worth presenting to the public. I hope it will stimulate thought about the potential of a planetary collision hypothesis and prompt a serious examination of plate tectonics theory.

Given my limited expertise, there are likely many clear errors and absurdities in my reasoning. I hope readers will be forgiving of my amateur status and provide constructive feedback, which I will gratefully accept and use to improve.

For me, as an outsider relying on common sense and imagination to produce such a detailed description of tectonic processes, this has been one of the most engaging endeavors of my life.

Thank you to the creators and institutions behind Google Earth! Thanks to all the owners and organizations of the images used in this paper! And thank you to all the readers of this paper!

(Final Draft, August 8, 2024)